

POLICY BRIEF

From Reactive to Resilient : Evidence-Based Winter Road Maintenance for the Kashmir Valley

Nadeem Akbar Najar

Arnab Jana

Devanathan Parthasarathy

Why this Policy Brief?

Winter road maintenance (WRM) is a lifeline for the economy, tourism, and public safety in the valley of Kashmir. It is supported under various government programs and departmental allocations, which primarily define "snow clearance" as a mechanized operation with specific machinery deployment. In practice, however, WRM operations vary widely depending on snowfall patterns, altitude, road priority, and other factors. In the current era of increasing climate variability, continued public investments in WRM are important to strengthen adaptive capacity. However, a critical question is: are investments in a uni-conception of snow clearance productive, sustainable, and equitable?

Drawing on an extensive study of WRM practices across the Kashmir Valley, integrating historical policy analysis, frontline implementation realities, robust design optimization, and economic evaluation, this policy brief highlights the need to structure public investments according to different typologies of WRM interventions. More importantly, the study flags the perverse incentives of reactive, uniform, and under-funded WRM approaches, which are driving operational inefficiencies, high accident rates, and unsustainable and inequitable resource allocation. The brief argues that WRM should be seen and invested in as part of the 'transportation ecosystem' rather than as isolated operations, and provides guiding principles for public investments in winter road maintenance.

The study is anchored by the Ashank Desai Centre for Policy Studies at IIT Bombay and developed through five published research papers spanning policy evolution, implementation barriers, robust design optimization, and economic analysis.

Introduction

Snow clearance is a critical service across the Kashmir Valley, especially in the high-altitude regions. As a result, WRM is a key intervention in transportation infrastructure, tourism continuity, and disaster management. Snow clearance is also supported under many central and state schemes related to roads, tourism, rural development, and disaster response, as well as through departmental budgets.

Figure 1: Growth of Machinery Procurement and Road Length for Snow Clearance in Kashmir (1987–2022). (Source: Content Analysis of Action Plans, 1987–2022; Mechanical Engineering Department, Kashmir)[1]

Traditionally, snow clearance served multiple functions. It regulated access to critical infrastructure, enabled emergency services, supported tourism, and ensured economic continuity. In the Kashmir Valley, which receives an average of 7 feet of snow annually, WRM has thus been a lifeline.

In recent times, WRM has evolved from the traditional idea of manual snow removal and now varies widely in its approach, technology, and resource intensity.

While some WRM operations rely on indigenous machinery for valley-wide clearance, many others involve purpose-built imported machines for high-altitude corridors and, in some cases, advanced technologies such as electrically heated pavement for frost-prone segments. This diversity requires an acknowledgment of different typologies of WRM interventions with varying impacts on sustainability, equity, energy costs, and productivity. Public funding for WRM should thus be in accordance with these typologies.

Collaborative Winter Road Maintenance Study

Anchored by the Ashank Desai Centre for Policy Studies at IIT Bombay, this study was conducted through five interconnected research objectives during 2022–26. It analyzed policy evolution through 387 coding units from archival records, conducted in-depth interviews with 13 snow clearance operators at Tangmarg Snow Control Station, employed Taguchi robust design optimization over four winter seasons (2017–2021), and carried out comprehensive cost-benefit analyses for fleet augmentation and heated pavement deployment.

Based on this collaborative effort, this policy brief presents a "typology of WRM interventions" and sets out guiding principles for government, departmental, and philanthropic programs to invest in winter road maintenance. The guiding principles are intended to guide programs to minimize the unintended negative impacts of WRM investment.

EVIDENCE FROM THE FIELD: BENEFITS AND RISKS

The Multi-faceted Benefits of Effective WRM

When WRM interventions are aligned with the local climatic factors and socio-economic conditions, they provide multiple transportation, economic, and safety benefits:

Resilience and Safety

- **Road safety and accident reduction:** Effective snow clearance reduces accidents by improving traction and visibility. Cost-benefit analysis shows significant savings from reduced accidents, with BCR of 22–32 for fleet augmentation.
- **Emergency access:** WRM ensures uninterrupted access to hospitals, water supply schemes, electrical installations, and other critical infrastructure during winter months.

Economic Continuity and Tourism

- **Tourism continuity:** Clear roads enable year-round access to tourist destinations like Gulmarg. The Gulmarg Development Authority data shows that enhanced WRM increases the Real Carrying Capacity (RCC) of tourist destinations, significantly boosting local revenue.
- **Economic activity:** WRM enables the movement of goods, services, and people, preventing economic disruptions that can last for days during heavy snowfall events.

Livelihood and Social Benefits

- **Employment generation:** WRM operations create direct employment for operators and drivers, as well as indirect employment through tourism and related sectors.
- **Social connectivity:** Snow-free roads enable access to education, healthcare, and social services, reducing isolation during winter months.

Findings

Case Study 1

Policy Evolution through Punctuated Equilibrium: From Manual to Mechanized Snow Clearance

Context: Before 1986, the Public Works Department used manual labourers to remove snow, a process that took many days. The government remained status quoist in its approach until a triggering event occurred [1].

Triggering Event: During the winter of 1985–86, the then Prime Minister of India visited Kashmir and was surprised to see roads closed due to snowfall for days together. He directed the government to look for machines that could clear snow.

Response: The Jammu and Kashmir Government deputed a team from the Mechanical Engineering Department to visit Germany to study snow clearance practices. Accordingly, the department procured 10 snow clearance machines, followed by 12 more in 1987.

Evolution: The policy progressed through five phases—manual clearance (pre-1986), transition to mechanisation (1987–2000), capacity building (2000–2010), modernisation (2010–2020), and sustainability (2020 onward). Each phase was driven by discrete events, including the 2005 Watego Nard avalanche, rather than gradual planning. This resulted in a 130% increase in machinery procurement between 2011 and 2021.

Policy Image Shift: The focus shifted from "clearing roads regardless of time taken" to "fast snow removal using machines," raising public expectations and driving further policy action. Policy image shifts consistently preceded venue shopping, expanding institutional involvement from PWD to MED Kashmir, BRO, PMGSY, SDRF, and Tourism Development Authorities [1].

WRM Typology: *Policy-driven mechanical snow clearance – punctuated equilibrium – capacity building – modernisation – sustainability.*

Recommendation for Public Funding: Recognize that policy change is driven by crises rather than planning. Establish proactive policy frameworks with contingency planning, regular equipment audits, and climate-adaptive strategies to prevent reactive, crisis-driven decision-making.

Case Study 2

Frontline Implementation Barriers and Coping Strategies: Snow Clearance Operators at Tangmarg

Context: The Tangmarg Snow Control Station is responsible for snow clearance on the 77 km Narbal–Gulmarg corridor, a high-altitude tourist route receiving heavy snowfall. Snow clearance operators face resource constraints, political interference, and public pressure.

Barriers Identified: Semi-structured interviews with 13 snow clearance operators and managers revealed multiple implementation barriers: political interference (MLAs/MPs demanding priority routes), lack of legal deterrence (wrongful parking, building code violations), aging fleets, absence of Road Weather Information Systems (RWIS), insufficient training, and public pressure amplified by social media [3].

Coping Strategies: Operators developed informal coping strategies—nighttime salting (to avoid interest group conflict with Sumo operators), phone deactivation (to manage political pressure), user categorization (to distinguish genuine emergencies from fake calls), and equipment improvisation (Indianizing imported machines using local spare parts).

Paradoxical Impact: These coping strategies maintain operational continuity but conceal systemic gaps in legal deterrence, political insulation, and training. Social media has raised public expectations beyond Lipsky's original street-level bureaucracy framework, creating unaddressed psychosocial stress among operators.

WRM Typology: *Human-centric – barrier-laden – coping-driven – reactive – politically influenced.*

Recommendation for Public Funding: Strengthen legal deterrence and political insulation; implement tiered accountability mechanisms (transparent route prioritization logs, mandatory supervisor sign-offs, independent audits); invest in RWIS; and design context-specific capacity building programs that address both technical and political mediation skills.

WRM: FROM REACTIVE TO RESILIENT

There is a wide diversity of WRM practices in Kashmir, with varying impacts. The evidence points to a spectrum along which WRM operations function, shaped by how they are executed, resourced, and integrated into the transportation ecosystem. Based on this, a broad typology of WRM interventions is presented below. Depending on the typology, a WRM strategy can be either a tool for resilience or a driver of resource depletion and inequity.

Typology 1: Manual/Contractor-based Snow Clearance

- **Infrastructure/Technology:** Manual labour, excavators with boom attachments

- **Location Context:** Narrow lanes, by-lanes, non-macadamized roads, low-priority rural roads
- **Purpose:** Basic access, emergency routes
- **Resource Intensity:** Low energy use, high labour
- **Response Time:** Several days to weeks
- **Economic Viability:** Low BCR
- **Overall Impact:** Public Good – Limited Scope
- **Funding Reference:** Pre-1986 policy

Typology 2: Indigenous Machinery-based Clearance

- **Infrastructure/Technology:** Snow plow trucks (military design), tractors with blades
- **Location Context:** Valley-wide, Priority-1, -2, and -3 roads
- **Purpose:** Mechanical snow removal
- **Resource Intensity:** Moderate energy use
- **Response Time:** 8–24 hours
- **Economic Viability:** BCR varies (indigenous only: 139)
- **Overall Impact:** Baseline – High Priority
- **Funding Reference:** Phase II-III policy

Typology 3: Mixed Fleet Clearance

- **Infrastructure/Technology:** 50% indigenous + 50% purpose-built machines
- **Location Context:** High-volume corridors, tourist destinations (e.g., Narbal–Gulmarg)
- **Purpose:** Fast mechanical clearance, reduced response time
- **Resource Intensity:** Moderate-high energy use
- **Response Time:** 20% reduction in response time
- **Economic Viability:** BCR = 22–32 (with tourism: 31.6)
- **Overall Impact:** Highly Cost-Effective – Top Priority
- **Funding Reference:** Taguchi optimization recommendation; CBA justification

Typology 4: All-Purpose-Built Clearance

- **Infrastructure/Technology:** Unimogs, snow cutters, blowers (imported from Germany/Switzerland)
- **Location Context:** High-altitude, strategic, and high-priority corridors
- **Purpose:** Maximum efficiency, reliable performance
- **Resource Intensity:** High energy use, high maintenance
- **Response Time:** 22% reduction in response time
- **Economic Viability:** BCR = 22
- **Overall Impact:** Effective but Costly – Strategic Use
- **Funding Reference:** Phase IV policy (modernisation)

Typology 5: Targeted Heated Pavement

- **Infrastructure/Technology:** Electrically heated pavement systems (Danfoss) with sensors
- **Location Context:** Frost-prone high-altitude segments (≤ 3 km validated hotspots)
- **Purpose:** Frost and black ice control, zero-chemical de-icing
- **Resource Intensity:** High energy use, minimal maintenance
- **Response Time:** Immediate response (sensor-activated)
- **Economic Viability:** Partial deployment (3 km): BCR = 1.6, NPV = ₹5,181 million; Full deployment (13 km): BCR = 0.8, NPV = –₹3,498 million
- **Overall Impact:** Viable for Hotspots Only – Conditional
- **Funding Reference:** Objective 5 techno-economic analysis

GUIDING PRINCIPLES FOR PUBLIC INVESTMENT IN WINTER ROAD MAINTENANCE PROGRAMS

Drawing on lessons from a comprehensive five-objective study of winter road maintenance in Kashmir, illustrated through case studies, this brief argues for continued public investment in WRM. It emphasizes that such investments should differentiate by typology, context, function, and design. The brief synthesises the following guiding principles for public investment in WRM:

Prioritize Mixed Fleet Clearance over Uniform or All-Imported Approaches

- a. Prioritize a **mixed fleet** configuration (50% indigenous + 50% purpose-built) which achieves 20% reduction in response time—nearly equivalent to all-imported fleets (22%) at substantially lower cost.
- b. Avoid all-imported fleet configurations for valley-wide clearance, as the marginal benefit (2% additional response time reduction) does not justify the significantly higher cost.
- c. Invest in purpose-built machines only for high-altitude, strategic corridors where reliability and performance are critical.
- d. Leverage the cost-effectiveness of indigenous machinery for valley-wide clearance while strategically deploying purpose-built machines for priority corridors.

Integrate Robust Design and Evidence-Based Decision Making

- a. Prioritize **fleet strength** [4] as the most critical lever for robustness (Taguchi rank 1; difference=3,442), followed by **fleet mix** (rank 2; difference=2,111) and **chemical treatment intensity** (rank 3; difference=871).
- b. Doubling fleet size reduces mean response time by 31%, providing the highest return on investment for enhancing WRM robustness.
- c. Use robust design optimization (Taguchi method) to evaluate WRM strategies under climatic uncertainty before making investment decisions.

Invest in Tiered Intervention Strategy

- a. **Tier 1 — Valley-wide:** Maintain mechanical clearance for all Priority-1, -2, and -3 roads using indigenous and mixed fleet configurations.
- b. **Tier 2 — Corridor augmentation:** Double fleet size for high-volume corridors (e.g., Narbal-Gulmarg) based on CBA results showing BCR of 22–32.
- c. **Tier 3 — Targeted hotspots:** Deploy electrically heated pavement only on validated frost-prone segments (≤ 3 km) rather than full-length deployment, as partial deployment is economically viable (BCR=1.6) while full deployment is not (BCR=0.8).

Strengthen Policy and Institutional Frameworks

- a. Recognize that policy change is driven by crises rather than planning. Establish **proactive policy frameworks** with contingency planning, regular equipment audits, and climate-adaptive

strategies.

b. Implement **tiered accountability** mechanisms: transparent route prioritization logs, mandatory supervisor sign-offs on politically requested detours, and annual independent audits.

c. Strengthen **legal deterrence** against wrongful parking, building code violations (roof snow directed onto roads), and unauthorized obstructions.

d. Establish a **dedicated funding stream** for WRM activities based on severity of winter weather conditions and traffic volumes, rather than ad-hoc crisis-driven allocations.

Invest in Technology and Capacity Building

a. Integrate **Road Weather Information Systems (RWIS)** for real-time road condition data, enabling proactive deployment and optimized resource allocation.

b. Transition capacity building from generic certifications to **context-specific competencies**, including climate-adaptive scenarios, extreme snowfall response drills, and political mediation training.

c. Establish **regular competency audits** to ensure skills translate into effective field deployment, addressing the "training-practice gap" identified by frontline operators.

d. Conduct **lifecycle assessments** of augmented WRM infrastructure to ensure long-term sustainability.

Adopt a Systems View for Investment

a. Prioritize WRM as part of an integrated **transportation ecosystem** rather than isolated operations.

b. Consider the interrelation between **road infrastructure, weather information, fleet deployment, operator capacity, and institutional coordination**.

c. Foster **partnerships between public agencies and private sector stakeholders** to share resources and expertise in WRM.

d. Implement a **mechanism for regular review and update of WRM policies**, incorporating feedback from maintenance personnel, stakeholders, and the community.

Case Study 3

Cost-Benefit Justification for Fleet Augmentation: Narbal–Gulmarg Corridor

Context: The Narbal–Gulmarg corridor (77 km) is a high-altitude, high-volume tourist route that experiences heavy snowfall and frequent frost formation. Current WRM practices are reactive, under-resourced, and technologically conservative.

Intervention: Doubling the fleet size from 14 to 28 machines for the Snow Control Station Tangmarg, and deploying a mixed fleet (50% indigenous + 50% purpose-built).

Economic Analysis: Cost-benefit analysis using traffic data, accident statistics, vehicle operating costs, and tourism revenue (Gulmarg Development Authority) revealed [5]:

- **Benefits:** Reduced travel time (₹951 million/year), reduced accidents (₹8 million/year), reduced vehicle operating costs (₹106 million/year), increased tourism activity (₹493 million/year).
- **Costs:** Capital cost (₹344 million), annual recurring cost (₹55 million).
- **Results (15-year, 7% discount rate):** NPV = ₹8,833 million; BCR = 21.6 (without tourism) to 31.6 (with tourism).

Monte Carlo Sensitivity Analysis: Confirmed economic viability across a wide range of scenarios, with BCR highly sensitive to winter severity and equipment type.

WRM Typology: *Mixed fleet – cost-benefit justified – economically viable – policy-enabling.*

Recommendation for Public Funding: Prioritize fleet augmentation for high-volume corridors based on robust economic justification. This approach ensures optimal resource allocation and maximizes public good.

Conclusion

Winter road maintenance is an integral part of transportation and economic landscape of J&K, playing a key role in adapting to and mitigating the impacts of climate change. The policy brief underscores the need for an investment approach that accounts for priorities, exclusions, and safeguards to maximize public good. A systems approach helps to ensure public investments strengthen road safety, economic continuity, and equity rather than becoming perverse incentives for reactive spending, unsustainable resource allocation, and inequity.

The findings [2] have direct policy implications for the **Indian Road Congress (IRC) Hill Road Manual** revision and offer a replicable framework for other climate-sensitive mountain regions (Himachal Pradesh, Uttarakhand, Ladakh, and international counterparts).

References

- [1] N. A. Najar, D. Parthasarathy, and A. Jana, "From shovels to snowploughs: the evolution of snow clearance infrastructure in Kashmir, India," *International Journal of Critical Infrastructures*, vol. 21, no. 3, pp. 209–227, Jan. 2025, doi: 10.1504/ijcis.2025.146871.
- [2] N. A. Najar, I. Nowsheri, A. Jana, and D. Parthasarathy. "TECHNO-ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF ELECTRICALLY HEATED PAVEMENT FOR SNOW CLEARANCE AT SUB-ZERO TEMPERATURES." *Indian Highways*, 53 (7), 58-74, Jul 2025.
- [3] N. A. Najar, A. H. Najar, I. A. Najar, A. Jana, and D. Parthasarathy, "Barriers to Winter Road Maintenance Policy Implementation and Coping Strategies Adopted by the Street-Level Bureaucrats: Evidence from Kashmir, India," *Transportation Research Record Journal of the Transportation Research Board*, Feb. 2026, doi: 10.1177/03611981251405251.
- [4] Najar, N. A., Jana, A., & Parthasarathy, D. Addressing climatic uncertainty through fleet optimization for robust winter road maintenance policy design. *Journal of Policy Modeling*, 47(1), 134-149, Jan 2025.
- [5] N. A. Najar, A. Jana, and D. Parthasarathy, "Investigating feasibility of fleet augmentation for mechanized snow clearance of roads: economic analysis and policy improvements," *Transportation in Developing Economies*, vol. 10, no. 2, Sep. 2024, doi: 10.1007/s40890-024-00217-x.

How to cite this policy brief:

Najar, N. A., Jana, A., & Parthasarathy, D. (2026). *From Reactive to Resilient: Evidence-Based Winter Road Maintenance for the Kashmir Valley*. Policy Brief, Ashank Desai Centre for Policy Studies, Indian Institute of Technology Bombay. <https://www.cps.iitb.ac.in> DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.21144692